

Article

Performances of Selective Mechanical Traps for Autumn Control of the Invasive Asian Hornet *Vespa velutina nigrithorax* in Western and Southern Europe

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Featured Application

This study aimed to provide beekeepers with guidance on selecting the most effective and selective trap–bait combinations to reduce *Vespa velutina nigrithorax* pressure on honey bee colonies. These findings support sustainable and biocide-free control strategies that can be directly implemented in apiaries to reduce stress on honey bee colonies while safeguarding other non-target insects.

Abstract

The invasive hornet *Vespa velutina nigrithorax* was first recorded in Spain in 2010 and in Italy in 2012. Control strategies to reduce *V. v. nigrithorax* infestation level in apiaries include nest neutralization and trapping of adult hornets. Trapping methods are simpler, more cost-effective, and can be implemented directly by beekeepers without the use of insecticides; however, they are usually poorly effective or selective. While assessing trap effectiveness is essential for reducing *V. v. nigrithorax* pressure on hives, evaluating trap selectivity is equally crucial to minimize the capture of non-target insects, such as honey bees and native hornets like *Vespa crabro*, which exist in a delicate balance with the honey bees. During autumn 2024, five combinations of commercially available mechanical traps, tested with both a homemade and a commercial bait, were evaluated in Spain and Italy to determine the most effective and selective option against *V. v. nigrithorax*. The mean daily capture rate was significantly lower in Italy (0.19 ± 0.07) than in Spain (1.82 ± 0.39). Significant differences were observed among the five trap–bait combinations ($p < 0.0001$), with the VelutinaTrap[®] (BeeVital GmbH, Vienna, Austria) associated with a homemade bait (sugar, yeast, and water) being the most effective. When trap design was considered independently of bait, VelutinaTrap[®] remained the most effective option ($p < 0.0001$). In contrast, no significant differences were detected between bait types when analyzed irrespective of trap design ($p = 0.524$). Concerning selectivity, even though all tested traps showed positive results against *A. mellifera*, the combination VelutinaTrap[®] associated with the homemade bait significantly outperformed in *V. crabro* selectivity. Further research is

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needed to develop more effective traps for capturing *V. v. nigrithorax* and to investigate environmental factors that influence variations in the attractiveness of the same trap and bait combinations across different seasons and geographical areas.

Keywords: *Vespa velutina nigrithorax*; trap design; bait efficacy; selectivity; bycatch; *Apis mellifera*; *Vespa crabro*; autumn trapping; invasive species management; citizen science

1. Introduction

Vespa velutina nigrithorax, also called Yellow-legged hornet, is a subspecies of *Vespa velutina* [1–3] and a social hornet naturally distributed in Southeast Asia [4]. It has been present in Europe since 2004 due to its accidental introduction from China [5–7]. *V. v. nigrithorax* is classified as an alien species, as it occurs outside its native range, and as an invasive species because its introduction poses a threat to biodiversity [8–11]. Arthropods (predominantly insects) represent the vast majority of biological invasions in Europe, accounting for approximately 94% of all alien terrestrial invertebrate species [12] due to ability to spread rapidly, high reproductive rates, varied diets, habitat adaptability, low detectability during trade, and capacity to establish new colonies with a single inseminated queen [13,14]. The first European country invaded by this hornet was France [15]. Several countries have reported the presence of *V. v. nigrithorax* within their territories, including Spain (2010) [16], Portugal (2011) [17], Belgium (2011) [18,19], Italy (2012) [19,20], Germany (2014) [21], Great Britain (2016) [22], The Netherlands (2017) [23], Switzerland (2017) [24], Luxembourg (2020) [25], Czechia (2023) [26], Hungary (2023) [27], and Austria (2024) [28]. In Italy, *V. v. nigrithorax* was first detected in Liguria in 2012 [29], spreading mainly along the coastal areas of the region and southwards [30], with a spread rate of approximately 10–20 km per year [31]. *V. v. nigrithorax* has also been reported in Piedmont (2013), Veneto and Lombardy (2016), Tuscany (2017), Emilia-Romagna (2022) and Sardinia (2025) [31]. In Spain, *V. v. nigrithorax* occupies a large part of the far north, most of Catalonia and the province of Cadiz [32], and Galicia—in the northwest of the country—is one of the most affected regions [33].

The infested areas exhibit predisposing environmental factors such as high humidity, temperatures around 20 °C [33,34], low precipitation levels [33], low altitude [35], and proximity to water sources [36], including coastal areas [35]. The spread of *V. v. nigrithorax* in Europe is causing economic and ecological losses, as well as posing threats to public health, including potentially fatal effects on humans [14,36]. *V. v. nigrithorax* was considered a generalist predator [1] that attacks various arthropods, removing the prey's thorax, which contains the nutrient-rich flight muscles [37]. *V. v. nigrithorax* invasion has caused significant problems as it preys on domestic honey bees (*Apis mellifera*) returning to their colonies [38,39], disrupts foraging activity and leads to colony collapse [40,41]. Previous studies based on the direct observations of *V. v. nigrithorax* adult foraging showed that the prey spectrum of this hornet varied with the level of urbanization: in urban areas, honey bees may constitute over 70% of its diet, while in forested habitats—where alternative prey species are more abundant—they account for around 30% [42]. This supported the idea that *V. v. nigrithorax* exhibits an opportunistic predation pattern [39], targeting species with high local density in the area, similar to other hornet species [43,44]. However, recent studies using DNA metabarcoding have shown that among pollinator insects, the most prevalent family identified was Apidae. This may indicate a highly selective predation behavior [45] considering that the honeybee DNA is detected also in all analyzed colonies irrespective

of collection site [46] and supports growing concern about the pressure this alien species places on *A. mellifera*.

European countries have implemented action plans to control, monitor, and potentially eradicate *V. v. nigrithorax* in regions where it is already established, as well as early detection strategies in areas where it has not yet been observed [9]. Control strategies to reduce infestation levels include the identification and neutralization of nests, as well as the trapping of adults. *V. v. nigrithorax* typically builds its nests in treetops [47], increasing the complexity of locating them. Nest neutralization is also expensive, involves specialized operators and equipment, and often needs the use of insecticides such as permethrins that could harm other insects and negatively affect environmental and human health [48–50]. Differently, trapping methods are cheaper and can be implemented by the beekeepers themselves.

To date, few studies have compared the effectiveness and selectivity of traps for *V. v. nigrithorax* and their attractants [29,34,35,51–55]. These studies showed different trap efficacies but in all cases low selectivity, with a high capture rate of non-target insects. While assessing trap effectiveness is essential for reducing the pressure of the *V. v. nigrithorax* on hives, it is equally important to evaluate the selectivity of these traps to lower the captures of native entomofauna [29,40,44,52,53]. The baits used to lure *V. v. nigrithorax* can also attract other insects, including honey bees, wild bees, flies, wasps, native hornets, and other taxa [44]. Additionally, the European native hornet, *V. crabro*, occupies the same ecological niche as *V. v. nigrithorax* [56] and may be caught in the same traps. Interspecific competition between these two hornet species is driven by spatial overlap, resulting in limited availability of nesting sites and prey resources [57,58]. However, *V. crabro* is native to Italy and Spain and has coevolved with local honey bees over time, resulting in a delicate balance of reciprocal adaptations and mild effect on honey bees [59]. This balance could be easily disrupted by the introduction of invasive hornets like *V. v. nigrithorax* and by the capture of *V. crabro* in mechanical traps placed in apiaries for *V. v. nigrithorax* control. Reducing the population of *V. crabro* in an area could inadvertently increase resources available for the growth of *V. v. nigrithorax* populations due to their niche overlap and interspecific competition [60]. This highlights the importance of designing traps and baits that specifically target *V. v. nigrithorax* while minimizing the impact on non-target species. Modern traps available on the market have attempted to improve their selectivity, often featuring size reducers at the entrance and smaller exit holes to allow non-target insects to escape, as well as filters over the baits to prevent the drowning of smaller non-target insects. On the other hand, the baits usually used are made from sugary or protein-based ingredients that can attract a wide range of insects [29] and must be adapted to the hornet's feeding behavior that change between the season, preferring carbohydrates when the adult population is high, and proteins when the brood is numerous [39,43,61].

Our study aimed to find the best combination between five trap and bait combinations in terms of effectiveness and selectivity to enhance the capture rate of *V. v. nigrithorax* and to lower the capture rate of non-target insects (*A. mellifera*, *V. crabro* and other insects) during autumn in Italy and Spain.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area and Experimental Design

This study was conducted over four consecutive weeks in autumn 2024 (from 14 October to 18 November). A total of 12 beekeepers (six from Italy and six from Spain) were selected based on their previous experience in monitoring *V. v. nigrithorax* and their proven ability to distinguish it morphologically from *V. crabro*. This study employed citizen science methodology. Participating beekeepers were selected based on their prior expertise and

received formal training regarding the deployment and monitoring of the traps. They checked the traps in their own apiary weekly, maintaining a minimum interval of seven days between checks. Two infested regions were identified in each country using information from the websites *Stop Velutina* [31] for Italy and *Avispa Asiatica* [62] for Spain. Based on these information, Liguria and Tuscany were selected in Italy, and Galicia and Asturias in Spain. Within each region, we chose three apiaries based on their *V. v. nigrithorax* infestation level (Table 1). In Italy, each beekeeper evaluated the infestation level in his apiary counting the number of *V. v. nigrithorax* in front of one line of hives for 20 min. The *V. v. nigrithorax* infestation level was characterized as low (average 1 or 2 hornets/20 min), medium (average 10 hornets/20 min) or high (>20 hornets/20 min). One apiary per infestation level was selected in each region.

Table 1. *V. v. nigrithorax* infestation level in the selected apiaries.

Country	Region	Municipality	<i>V. v. nigrithorax</i> Infestation Level
Italy	Liguria	Monterosso al Mare	Low
		Maggiano	Medium
		Ameglia	High
	Tuscany	Massa ¹	High
		Massa ²	Medium
Spain	Galizia	Mulazzo	Low
		Vigo	Medium
		A Caniza	Low
	Asturias	Lugo	High
		Llanera	High
		Gijón	Low
		Siero	Medium

^{1,2} Two apiaries were selected from the same municipality (Massa, Tuscany, Italy): one closer ¹ to the coast and one farther ².

2.2. Trap Designs and Trap–Bait Combinations

Five different combinations of mechanical traps and baits were tested. Three commercially available mechanical traps were selected: VelutinaTrap[®] (BeeVital GmbH, Vienna, Austria) (B), VespaCatch Select[®] (Véto-pharma SAS, Palaiseau, France) (V), and GardApis Sentinel[®] (Gard'Apis, Genouille, France) (G) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Mechanical traps tested: (a) Vespa Catch Select[®] (V trap); (b) GardApis Sentinel[®] (G trap); (c) VelutinaTrap[®] (B trap).

Only selective mechanical traps were included, defined by three design characteristics: (1) an appropriately sized entrance to prevent the entry of larger non-target insects/animals, (2) exit holes to allow smaller non-target insects to escape, and (3) a system to prevent insects from drowning in the bait. B trap and V trap are considered more hygienic because

they include a filter over the bait that separates the bait and the capture areas and prevent non-target insects from drowning (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Filters: (a) Vespa Catch Select[®] (V trap); (b) GardApis Sentinel[®] (G trap); (c) VelutinaTrap[®] (B trap).

The G trap lacks this filter; therefore, bait was solidified with gelatin, as recommended by the manufacturer. Trap entrances were adjusted to 0.9 cm (V trap), 0.8 cm (G trap, using the red nozzle), and 1.3 cm (B trap, without adapter). Two bait types were evaluated: a commercial bait provided by the manufacturers (available only for B and V traps) and a homemade bait composed of 1 L of water, 400 g of sugar, and 10 g of baker’s yeast [52,55]. Each trap was filled with the volume recommended by the manufacturer (B: ~400 mL; V: ~200 mL; G: filled to capacity). Commercial baits were used following the suppliers’ instructions. The five tested trap–bait combinations were: B trap with commercial bait (BC), B trap with homemade bait (BH), V trap with commercial bait (VC), V trap with homemade bait (VH), and G trap with homemade bait (GH) (Table 2).

Table 2. The five different bait-trap combinations tested.

	BC	BH	VC	VH	GH
Trap	Beevital (B)	Beevital (B)	VespaCatch Select (V)	VespaCatch Select (V)	Gardapis Sentinel (G)
Bait	Commercial (C)	Homemade (H)	Commercial (C)	Homemade (H)	Homemade (H)
Adapter	None (1.3 cm)	None (1.3 cm)	Diameter = 0.9 cm	Diameter = 0.9 cm	Red nozzle (0.8 cm)
Number of entrances	4	4	2	2	2

2.3. Field Experimental Setup

The beekeepers tested all five combinations of baits and traps simultaneously, placing them at a height of approximately 1–1.5 m and spacing them about 3 m apart, following the method described by Liroy et al. (2020) [53]. Traps were placed under tree foliage and hung from branches to protect them from weather conditions such as wind and rain. During each inspection, the beekeepers noted on pre-filled forms the inspection date, the number of days between inspections the number of insects captured (*V. v. nigrithorax*, *V. crabro*, *A. mellifera*, and other insects) for each trap and bait combination.

2.4. Data Analysis

Capture rates were calculated for the target species (*V. v. nigrithorax*) and non-target species (*V. crabro* and *A. mellifera*) as the number of individuals captured per trap per day. This was derived by dividing the total number of specimens recorded between inspections by the number of active trapping days. Trap efficacy was defined as the magnitude of the *V. v. nigrithorax* capture rate. We measured the number of *V. v. nigrithorax* captured per trap per day in both countries to assess the efficacy of each trap and bait combination (BC, BH, GH, VC, and VH). A higher efficacy was associated with a greater number of

V. v. nigrithorax captured per day. We verified the normality of distributions using the Anderson-Darling test and performed ANOVA and Tukey's post hoc test to compare the efficacy of the traps without considering the different baits, and the efficacy of the five different combinations of traps and baits. We also performed *T*-test to compare the efficacy of the baits without considering the traps design. The effect of country (Italy or Spain) on the *V. v. nigrithorax* capture rate was assessed using a *t*-test, while the effect of infestation level at each apiary was evaluated using ANOVA. Finally, we evaluated changes in the *V. v. nigrithorax* capture rate at each inspection, considering only bait type and trap design separately. Selectivity was calculated as the ratio between the capture rate of *V. v. nigrithorax* and the capture rates of *V. crabro* and *A. mellifera*, respectively. Additionally, we calculated a combined selectivity index as the ratio of the *V. v. nigrithorax* capture rate to the sum of *V. crabro* and *A. mellifera* capture rates. Normality was tested with the Anderson–Darling test, followed by ANOVA, Levene's test, Welch's F test, and Bayes factor analysis to detect significant differences among traps and trap–bait combinations. Tukey's post hoc test identified the most effective and selective trap designs and combinations. Additional *t*-tests compared bait selectivity independently of trap design, and selectivity of the five trap–bait combinations relative to "other insects," with non-target captures expressed in binary format (presence = 1, absence = 0).

3. Results

3.1. Overall Captures

A total of 84 traps were placed, 42 in Spain and 42 in Italy: 12 BC, 12 BH, 12 VC, 12 VH and 12 GH. Beekeepers inspected their traps at an average interval of 7.28 ± 1.03 (SD) days between checks. Across the study period, 1,704 *V. v. nigrithorax*, 745 *V. crabro*, and 395 *A. mellifera* were captured in all the traps in both countries. The mean number (\pm SEM) of individuals captured per trap per day, irrespective of trap design and the bait type, was 1.04 ± 0.21 for *V. v. nigrithorax*, 0.44 ± 0.07 for *V. crabro*, and 0.24 ± 0.08 for *A. mellifera* (Figure 3). The capture rate of *V. v. nigrithorax* followed a normal distribution in both countries throughout all the study period in all trap and bait combinations.

Figure 3. The number of insects (*V. v. nigrithorax*, *V. crabro* and *A. mellifera*) captured per day per trap. Left (green) *V. v. nigrithorax*, center (orange) *V. crabro* and right *A. mellifera*. Dots represent mild outliers; asterisks represent extreme outliers.

3.2. Efficacy of Trap–Bait Combinations

The mean daily capture rate of *V. v. nigrithorax* for each trap–bait combination was BH (3.04 ± 0.78), BC (1.64 ± 0.63), VH (0.33 ± 0.13), VC (0.11 ± 0.04), and GH (0.09 ± 0.05) (Figure 4). ANOVA test demonstrated a statistically significant difference among the five trap and bait combinations ($p < 0.0001$). Tukey’s post hoc test showed that BH differed significantly from VC ($p < 0.0001$), VH ($p < 0.001$), and GH ($p < 0.0001$) with BH showing consistently higher *V. v. nigrithorax* capture rates. In contrast, BC did not differ significantly from any group and VC, VH, and GH resulted statistically similar.

Figure 4. Efficacy of the five trap and bait combinations (BC, BH, GH, VC, and VH) in capturing *V. v. nigrithorax* in both Italy and Spain throughout all the study period. Dots represent mild outliers; asterisks represent extreme outliers.

3.3. Temporal Variation in Captures of *V. v. nigrithorax*

The daily capture rate of the yellow-legged hornet, *V. v. nigrithorax*, exhibited significant temporal variation across the four inspection periods, revealing distinct patterns influenced by bait type and trap design.

3.3.1. Effect of Bait Type

Analysis of the captures based solely on the bait formulation revealed a clear temporal dynamic. The commercial bait elicited a significant increase in hornet captures during the second inspection period, with an average of 1.53 ± 1.06 individuals captured per trap across all apiaries (Figure 5). After this peak, capture rates decreased and stabilized at a lower level for the rest of this study. In contrast, the homemade bait showed a less pronounced peak and a generally lower, though similar, trajectory. Despite this observable trend, a statistical comparison of total captures between the two bait types revealed no significant difference in trapping efficacy ($p = 0.524$).

Figure 5. Mean daily capture rate of *V. v. nigrithorax* throughout the four sequential inspection periods, stratified by bait type (commercial vs. homemade).

3.3.2. Effect of Trap Design

The trap design had a far greater influence on capture success than the type of bait used. Throughout this study, the B trap design outperformed the others consistently, accounting for the majority of total captures. Like the overall population activity trend, the B trap showed a distinct capture peak during the second inspection (2.61 ± 1.11 individuals). This was followed by a decline and stabilization in later periods (Figure 6). ANOVA confirmed that the differences in mean capture rates among the three trap designs were highly statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). Post hoc analysis using the Tukey significant difference test revealed that the B trap captured significantly more hornets than the G trap ($p < 0.001$) and the V trap ($p < 0.0001$). There was no significant difference between the capture rates of the G and V traps.

Figure 6. *V. v. nigrithorax* daily capture rate throughout the four inspections considering only the trap design.

3.4. Geographic Differences (Italy vs. Spain)

The analysis revealed significant geographic disparities in the capture rates of *V. v. nigrithorax* among the populations studied in Italy and Spain. In both countries, the distribution of daily capture rates per trap adhered to a normal distribution, confirming the suitability of parametric statistical tests for comparative analysis (Figure 7). Despite the similar distribution patterns, the intensity of captures differed drastically. The mean daily capture rate in Spain was an order of magnitude higher ($M = 1.82$, 95% CI [1.04, 2.60]) than that recorded in Italy ($M = 0.19$, 95% CI [0.05, 0.34]) (Figure 8). An independent samples *t*-test confirmed that this difference was highly statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$).

Figure 7. Frequency distribution of *V. v. nigrithorax* daily capture rates per trap, demonstrating a normal distribution for both the Italian (blue lines) and Spanish (green lines) study sites.

Figure 8. Boxplot of capture rates of *V. v. nigrithorax* capture rate per trap per day in Italy and Spain. Dots represent mild outliers; asterisks represent extreme outliers.

3.5. Effect of Local Apiary Infestation Level

To assess whether local hornet pressure influenced trap efficacy, apiaries were categorized into three levels of infestation (Low, Medium, High) based on the direct observation of the beekeepers on the number of *V. v. nigrithorax* individuals in the apiary at the time of this study. ANOVA revealed no statistically significant relationship between the pre-defined local infestation level and the mean daily capture rate of *V. v. nigrithorax* ($p = 0.075$).

3.6. Selectivity of Traps and Baits

The selectivity of the different trap–bait combinations was evaluated by analyzing the bycatch of non-target species, specifically the honey bee (*A. mellifera*) and the European hornet (*V. crabro*).

3.6.1. Bycatch of *A. mellifera*

The potential impact on pollinators constituted a primary concern. The statistical analysis confirmed that the five trap–bait combinations (BC; BH; VC; VH; GH) did not differ significantly in their capture rates of *A. mellifera* (One-way ANOVA, $F(4, 225) = p = 0.119$). A robust Welch's ANOVA substantiated the null result ($p = 0.095$). This conclusion was further reinforced by a Bayes Factor of 0.035, which provided substantial evidence in support of the null hypothesis that all combinations are equally selective, or non-selective, for honey bees. Furthermore, no substantial discrepancy was observed when evaluating the combined bycatch of *A. mellifera* and *V. crabro* ($F(4, 225) = 2.05, p = 0.088$).

3.6.2. Bycatch of *V. crabro*

In contrast, a significant difference was detected in the capture rates of the native European hornet, *V. crabro*, across the five trap and bait combinations ($F(4, 225) = 3.11, p = 0.016$). Post hoc Tukey's test showed significant differences in *V. crabro* selectivity between BH and VC ($p = 0.038$), VH ($p = 0.040$), and GH ($p = 0.029$). No other significant differences were found among the remaining group pairs (Figure 9).

Figure 9. *V. v. nigrithorax* selectiveness of the five trap and bait combinations (BC, BH, VH, VC, and GH) respect separately *V. crabro*. Dots represent mild outliers; asterisks represent extreme outliers.

3.6.3. Effect of Trap Design and Bait Type on Selectivity

ANOVA analysis revealed a statistically significant difference between group means the three different traps designs without considering the bait and the *V. v. nigrithorax* trapping selectiveness ($F(2, 227) = 3.62, p = 0.028$). Post hoc Tukey's test indicated a significant difference between "B" and "V" groups ($p = 0.038$). No other significant differences were observed between "B" and "G" ($p = 0.116$) or "G" and "V" ($p = 0.9998$). There was no difference between the G and V traps ($p = 0.9998$). However, the type of bait (commercial versus homemade) did not have a statistically significant effect on selectivity for *V. crabro* ($p = 0.407$).

4. Discussion

This citizen science study demonstrates that trap design is the primary factor influencing the efficacy of capturing the invasive yellow-legged hornet, *V. v. nigrithorax*, during autumn. The B trap, particularly when baited with a homemade solution (BH), constituted the most effective combination. Furthermore, all tested configurations showed relatively high selectivity, minimizing bycatch of the honey bee.

The decision to test a modified VespaCatch[®] trap (V-trap) was informed by previous studies. These studies noted the trap's high capture rates; however, they also reported problematic bycatch of non-target species [53,55]. The inclusion of dimensional adapters in all our trap designs was intended to enhance selectivity. These adapters, designed to allow the entry of both workers and gynes (future queens) which are active in autumn [36], also contributed to a key mechanism for increasing efficacy: the retention of live hornets. These captured individuals likely act as live lures, continuously releasing pheromones that recruit nestmates, a well-documented behavior in eusocial insects [63].

The autumn sampling period was selected deliberately as it represents a peak in both hornet population size [64] and predation pressure on apiaries [37]. Furthermore, warmer autumn temperatures help maintain the stability and olfactory profile of fermented bait solutions, ensuring their effectiveness throughout this study [53]. While commercial baits are widely marketed, we included a homemade bait based on previous successful reports [55] to provide a cost-effective alternative for beekeepers.

Despite observing more *V. v. nigrithorax* than non-target species (*V. crabro* or *A. mellifera*), the absolute capture rates were moderate. This discrepancy, notably in Italy where hornets were frequently observed foraging on natural resources but not entering traps, can be attributed to several factors. First, the abundance of natural, sugar-rich food sources in autumn, such as ripe fruit and nectar, provides intense competition for artificial baits [43]. *V. velutina* frequently exploits fruits as a source of sugars, causing direct damage to fruit production, particularly in vineyards and orchards. In Galicia, Spain, and Portugal, significant economic losses have been reported in grapes, apples, and other fruits due to hornet foraging [65–67]. To mitigate these impacts, management techniques such as exclusion systems using anti-hail nets have been tested in vineyards, demonstrating increased yields by effectively reducing hornet and bird damage. Second, adverse weather conditions, including rainfall which curtails insect flight activity [33], reduced trapping efficiency on some days. Finally, the ongoing neutralization of nests by local authorities during the study period may have dynamically altered local hornet densities [65], confounding capture rates.

Our results suggest that the efficacy of *V. v. nigrithorax* traps depends more on design than bait type. The B trap consistently outperformed the V and G traps, likely due to its structural features. These features include a greater number of entrance holes and larger diameters. These characteristics may facilitate hornet entry while maintaining selectivity [53]. Notably, combining the B trap with homemade bait (BH) produced the highest capture rates, suggesting a synergistic effect between trap morphology and bait composition. In

contrast, commercial bait alone did not significantly enhance trap performance, suggesting that bait effectiveness depends on the trap's specific design [34]. These findings underscore the importance of selecting appropriate trap designs for effectively managing *V. v. nigrithorax* populations and suggest that optimizing bait composition alone may be insufficient. The observed synergy between the trap and bait underscores the necessity of integrated approaches when developing control strategies. Our results are consistent with previous studies showing that the structural characteristics of traps are a key factor in hornet capture efficiency while the role of bait remains context-dependent [53]. Overall, these insights can inform practical recommendations for beekeepers and guide future research on improving trapping methods for managing invasive hornets.

Capture rates for *V. v. nigrithorax* were higher in Spain than in Italy. This pattern may reflect differences in regional infestation levels, but could also be influenced by contrasting local environmental conditions in Central-North Italy and Northern Spain during the same sampling period. There were no significant correlations between *V. v. nigrithorax* capture rates in the different trap and bait combinations and the infestation levels reported by beekeepers. This suggests that visual assessments of infestation levels are often imprecise and can fluctuate rapidly due to environmental factors such as temperature, food availability, and precipitation [33–35].

All traps captured only small numbers of *A. mellifera* individuals, and there were statistically significant differences between trap types. The low incidence of *A. mellifera* individuals collected suggests that all the traps tested are relatively selective, with minimal bycatch, and that all tested traps are safe for use in apiaries, posing minimal risk to honeybee populations. This selectivity likely stems from a combination of appropriately sized entry holes that allow smaller, non-target insects to escape and filters that prevent insects the size of honey bees from entering and drowning. Instances of *A. mellifera* presence within the traps were rare and usually accidental, occurring in only one out of 48 inspections. These cases were associated with mechanical blockages in smaller trap components, which temporarily trapped individual bees and prevented other insects from passing through (Figure 10). These findings are consistent with previous studies showing that traps with specific structural features can selectively capture *V. velutina* while reducing the incidental capture of non-target species, such as *A. mellifera* [55].

Figure 10. An example of anecdotal and accidental capture of *A. mellifera* in B trap due to mechanical issues.

The number of *V. crabro* individuals collected was low, suggesting a higher selectivity compared to other trapping systems, such as the classical bottle with the yellow cap or the VespaCatch [53]. Regarding selectivity for *V. crabro*, only the BH combination showed a statistically significant difference compared to VC, VH, and GH, indicating that the addition of homemade bait to the B trap increased selectivity, confirming the same results found in the efficacy evaluation. When considering only the trap design we found the B trap to be more selective than the others despite the presence of larger holes in the entrance. It should be considered that the average size of the abdomen of *V. crabro* is larger than that of *V. v. nigrithorax* [68] suggesting that this selectivity could be linked to other characteristics of the trap.

However, when considering selectivity for both *V. crabro* and *A. mellifera*, no significant differences were found. Although the BH trap appears more selective for *V. crabro*, the statistical significance is lost when including *A. mellifera* data. This result may be related to the higher *A. mellifera* capture rates in the B trap, due to the mechanical blockages previously described.

We found no significant differences in the capture of other non-target insects across trap–bait combinations. Overall, bycatch was low, with few insects found in the capture cages. However, small insects may pass through the filter and drown in the bait, suggesting that the filter is not fully effective in reducing trap selectivity. Further study, counting the exact number of different non-target species not only inside the capture chambers but also inside the bait and the filters are needed to correctly evaluating the selectivity of these traps not only respect *V. crabro* and *A. mellifera*, but also in general respect all the other insects as performed in previous studies on trapping efficacy and selectivity [53,55].

5. Conclusions

This citizen science study highlights that trap design is the most critical factor influencing the capture rate of *V. v. nigrithorax* during autumn in Western and Southern Europe. Among the tested configurations, the B trap—especially when combined with the homemade bait (BH)—proved to be the most effective trap type, suggesting a synergistic effect between trap morphology and bait composition. Regional differences in capture rates, as well as the lack of correlation with beekeeper-reported infestation levels, together with the influence of environmental factors such as food availability, weather conditions, and nests neutralization efforts underline the complexity of predicting and monitoring the spread of *V. v. nigrithorax* populations. The results of this study suggest that focusing on improving trap design may be more effective than optimizing bait composition. Future research should primarily aim to refine trap structures and secondarily explore combining effective trap types with context-specific baits. The B trap combined with homemade bait (BH) showed slightly higher selectivity for *V. crabro*. All tested traps showed high selectivity, with low bycatch of *A. mellifera*, confirming that they are safe for use in apiaries. Nevertheless, the capture of occasional small insects drowned inside the bait highlights the need for further studies to assess selectivity for a wider range of non-target insects, including those small enough to pass through filters, in order to refine future trap designs. These findings provide practical recommendations for beekeepers to reduce *V. v. nigrithorax* pressure on honey bee colonies, contributing to sustainable and environmentally responsible management of this invasive species.

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